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THE PROCESS OF FINANCING THE SOCIAL SPHERE IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This article describes in detail the process of financing the social sphere in different countries, as well as directions, models and programs to support the social sphere through the ongoing policy. The purpose of this research is consideration in financing methods of social enterprises for competitiveness in provision of the highest quality services and improvement of living standards.

Keywords: social institutions, modernization, federal programs, benefits, financial safety.

Introduction

At present, both the authorities and society are coming to an understanding that not so much abstract indicators of the economic and technical development of the state as a healthy spiritual, moral, social and physical state of the individual should be the goal and criterion for the correctness of all decisions made. Moreover, in the course of an active discussion about the directions and methods of modernizing the country, it became obvious that, first of all, it is in the labor and creative potential of a person, and not in the quantitative growth of the scale of the economy, that the main opportunities for transforming the whole society for the better live. It is appropriate to rely on the theoretical and methodological foundations of spatial policy developed by local and foreign scientists in order to form and regulate the social infrastructure and solve its problems rationally. The prevalence of socially oriented mixed economy in many industrialized countries made it possible to declare a high level of social protection of citizens, the idea of "welfare for all" as the goals of social development.

Theoretical aspects of research

The social sphere is a complex of networks, institutions, offices and organizations that are directly related to each other and determine the lifestyle, standard of living, welfare and needs of people. The Republic of Uzbekistan was justified by the fact that it is important to expand the scope of social sector financing to become one of the countries with medium-term income by 2030. The state must act as a prerequisite for socio-economic development, with a focus on education, science, health, and culture as the basis for sustained, high-quality and safe economic growth, as the state implements its national interests. Increasing the efficiency of financing in the social sector is primarily a human factor. Social sector financing is a whole set of primary impacts on the development of the national economy⁵.

"The intellectual, spiritual culture of the nation today, more than ever, is becoming the main factor in socio-economic progress. Modernization is impossible without a sufficient general cultural level of the population" – this idea is expressed by Academician O.T. Bogomolov⁶. The approach towards financing of the investment processes in the social sphere has been changing for some time. G.A. Akhinov thinks that the main technology in performing state social functions used to

⁵ <https://ijecm.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/71216.pdf>

⁶ Богомолов О.Т. Потенциал национальной культуры в обновлении российского общества // Модернизация

России: социально-гуманитарные измерения / под ред. акад. Н.Я. Петракова; РГНФ; РАН. – М.: СПб: Нестор История, 2011. – С. 52-53.

be the technology of "social transfers, which were paid to the most vulnerable categories of population, but now the active state support must include investments in people and human capital"⁷. An investment approach in performing state social functions usually means that the state tries to participate minimally in financing of the social programs that include compensation payments for needy people. The governments of some countries often interfere in activities of corporate business and private companies. The main direction of the state social policy is focusing on creation and development of "middle class", which must be the main element in the development of the society. This kind of management of the state social policy has investment features but not consumer ones. The main aim of financing of the social investment activity at the state level is reaching a more rational form of interaction between investors, the state and consumers in the process of improving the quality of living and the standards of living. Thus, when the state social function is performed, it is necessary pass from a consumer approach to an investment one.

The USA experience

The social assistance system in the United States is characterized by various federal and local programs aimed at providing assistance to vulnerable groups of the population. A major role in this is played by large-scale federal programs, such as the Food Stamp Program or the Temporary Assistance for Needy Families program.

Implementation of federal social assistance programs is regulated by federal laws. For example, the Temporary Assistance for Needy Families program, along with the Personal Responsibility and Workability Act, includes food assistance. These programs are financed partly from the federal budget and partly from the state budget[1]. The total percentage of financing depends on the socio-economic situation in a particular country [2][3]. The implementation of federal programs in a particular state is significantly affected by the initiative of state administrations to change or supplement program elements. This initiative is reflected in the development of proposals for the implementation of regional demonstration projects. By implementing this application, the state seeks to improve the effectiveness of the federal program in relation to the conditions of the local community, to make the social assistance provided within the program more targeted and fair⁸. In turn, by accepting the state-supported application and reviewing the results of the demonstration project, the federal center - in addition to helping to improve the effectiveness of federal programs in this area - also contributes to the acquisition of valuable practical information for the modernization of federal programs.

The Canadian experience

Modern world experience shows that various systems of managing the social and cultural sphere are

successfully operating in developed countries abroad. Most of them include various social security institutions. These systems differ only in which of these institutions prevails[4]. Canada is one of the countries with the highest standard of living and a good system for the development of the socio-cultural sphere. However, since the last decade of the 20th century, its position among the world's "richest" countries has weakened somewhat. The general level of development of the social sector, the principles of financing and organization of health and higher education, the influence of the state's socio-economic policy on the redistribution of income, all this distinguishes Canada from the leaders. The existing system of social organization of society is closer to Western Europe than to America. In Canada, more than 8% of low-income people receive assistance through Social Security, the government's program to support those in need. Benefits are given to 4 categories - single parent with 2 children, single able-bodied, single disabled and able-bodied family with 2 children, benefits include general, additional, child and tax benefits. Food, transportation, daily necessities and housing expenses are also taken into account. There are also special allowances - buying furniture, moving, training, compensation for damages, laundry or paying for a dentist are considered as such allowances.

According to Canada's nationwide program, the federal government is required to cover half of the costs of the provinces to provide various social assistance to low-income citizens. In addition to the state pensions for age, the system of labor pensions has been established, and in order to ensure the monthly income of all citizens over 65 years of age not less than a certain minimum amount, guaranteed supplements to the old-age pensions paid to them. A number of conditions contribute to the rapid development of the social sector in Canada: the relatively low unemployment rate, combined with moderate inflation, allowed the introduction of new social programs and increased spending for these purposes without the risk of budget deficits. In Canada, the public social security system is more developed than in the United States. Canada, which increased the share of social spending by 24.5%

At the beginning of the 21st century, it retained its "middle" position among the most developed countries in the world. In other countries, for example, the Netherlands, Sweden, Denmark, Germany, France, Italy, the level of social spending was from 26 to 35% of GDP.

The experience of Western European countries

In Scandinavia, support programs for families with children are part of the welfare state programs[5][6]. They are universal in nature (regardless of family income), aimed at supporting the middle class, and currently have a clear value component - eliminating gender inequality, supporting responsible fatherhood and parenthood[7]. In Sweden,

⁷ <https://www.revis-taespacios.com/a19v40n10/19401024.html>

⁸ Ижтимоий ёрдамнинг адолатли таъминланиши остида давлат бошқаруви органлари нафақат ёрдамга

муҳтожларга ёрдам кўрсатишни, балки ишлаётган резидентларнинг ижтимоий солиқ юкини камайтиришни ҳам тушунилади.

benefits are paid to both biological and adoptive parents. They are fully protected against dismissal for a year, in case of dismissal they are paid 90% of their salary (from the social security fund) for 9-18 months and they are charged a minimum rent for one month. Parental leave for child care (which can be taken by one of the parents), as well as special paternity leave.[8]. The monthly additional payment is paid per child and corresponds to the number of children in the family. A single-parent family also has the opportunity to receive child support benefits. Parents can choose a community-run day care or family education allowance. If parents find it necessary to reduce their working hours to take care of a child, their income is partially called family education allowance. When caring for a sick child, the parents' loss of wages is compensated by a daily allowance in proportion to the wages.

Conclusion

Universal social protection programs have not lost their relevance. However, it is recognized that the distribution methods of social assistance create dependency, so targeted programs for the needy are provided to encourage employment. In addition to targeted programs, contract-type programs aimed at transitioning from labor assistance to social sphere and economy integration, to social investments are being actively developed. They also contribute to the development of a network of non-profit social institutions that allow municipalities and utilities to enter into contracts for the provision of services on a competitive basis.

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